

NATIONAL CASTLE CLOTHES

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ABSTRACT

This article provides detailed information about the history of Uzbek national

costumes and embroidered shirts belonging to the Nurata embroidery school.

KEYWORDS

ethnos, nimshoyi, jorma, museum, islami gul, kolenkor, kimkhob

INTRODUCTION

*Relevance and importance for us
an issue that will never be lost
our children are independent-minded,
modern knowledge and skills
occupied, solid vital
have a position, real people
is the task of educating.*

Sh.Mirziyoev

have a centuries-old history. Although each ethnic group has its own distinctive headgear, the presence of sarpo in the general character of the ethnoses living in the region indicates that their historical destiny and culture have been close for a long time.

The clothes of the Uzbek people are very diverse, colorful and attractive. They consist of men's, women's and children's clothing and are also classified according to the seasons of human life. Clothing also reflects a person's social status,

the place and time in which he lived, and the happy or sad events in his life. At all times, depending on the clothes, a person can know which social category he belongs to.

In historical clothing, ornaments represented not only the social origin of their owner, i.e. their class, but also the figurative meaning, as well as the aesthetic taste of the people. As time went on, they improved, their species multiplied, and their forms became more complex. In particular, they appeared in the form of bracelets, rings, earrings, embroidered or printed embroideries, printed pictures, embossed ornaments, which can be taken off and fastened to the body.

The main fabrics used in the sewing of Uzbek national clothes in the XIX century are yarn, silk and woolen fabrics. There are many types of yarn fabrics. Especially light brown, yellow tones are common.

Due to the import of yarn and other fabrics from Russia to Central Asia in the first half of the XIX century, in the late XIX and early XX centuries, the locals wore mainly factory-made yarns: chit, boz, kolenkor, raw surp. Boy- rich people esa kimxob , silk , satin, velvet , rang- barang movuts buy be beginners . That's it despite , artisans dastgo h idan came out local fabric : cloth , gray , nimshoyi , adras , beqasam , kimkhob , honatlas , katakshoyi such as different variety need big

which was .

Patterns of ancient dresses are still preserved mainly in the clothes of the elderly and young children. For example, in the Zeravshan oasis, dresses with white collars are mostly worn.

It is known that the Uzbek people dress separately in their national ceremonies. Due to the natural conditions, the national costumes of the people of the province were also suitable for the natural conditions. The bright, light colors, loose shape and unique variety of embroidery of the garment fabric testify to the high taste of the people.

Today, the shirt, which belongs to the Nurata embroidery school, located in the ethnography department of the State Museum of History and Culture of Navoi region, attracts the attention of many tourists. This embroidered dress , sewn in gray fabric in the style of the XIX century, was worn mainly by brides and middle-aged women. The floral images on the dress are embroidered using colored silk threads. The chest and most of the shirt are embroidered on a long ribbon in the style of embroidery. Also, the outer middle part of the two sleeves on the shirt has been left open using ribbon embroidery to make it easier to do household chores.

In embroidery, each pattern has its own history and philosophy of creation. Naqsh is an Arabic word meaning "image, flower". Each pattern and its elements have long been described

by our grandmothers as a symbol of something and reality. Patterns are created by placing, comparing, and combining simple elements in a specific order, whether simple or complex. The patterns will also have unique names and meanings. Patterns play a key role in the decoration of applied art. When decorating an item with patterns, it is chosen depending on the shape, function of the item and what material it is made of.

This national costume is more reflective of plant motifs i.e. "Islamic flowers". The Islamic flowers, in turn, are in a form that connects in two directions. Also, in Nurota's embroidery, the element "Leaf" gives a bright look, and in this dress, it has its own look and combines with unusual colors.

Such embroidered dresses have become a true work of art for hundreds of years. Embroidered dresses are distinguished by their brightness, harmony of colors. The peculiarity of Nurata's embroidery is that he also used the method of embroidery with great skill.

It is still a tradition among women and girls to wear embroidered shirts, jackets, carry embroidered bags and carry embroidered purses. Uzbek sarpos have a modern look and are especially associated with European clothing. National costumes are more diverse in women's sarpos in more remote rural areas. When we studied the history of clothing, it was known that for a very long time, in ancient times, our ancestors wore white cotton dresses.

Our highest goal is to pass on the history of our national handicrafts to the younger generation of the ancient culture and traditions of our grandmothers, which have developed and inherited over the centuries.

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